

ARYLTHIOPYRUVIC ACIDS AND SOME OF THEIR CORRESPONDING NITRILES

BY P. N. BHARGAVA, K. N. PERMESWARAN AND S. VENKATARAMAN

2-*o*-Tolylimino-3-*o*-tolyl-4-thiazolidone and 2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone, prepared according to the method of Bhargava *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 2355) have been utilised for the synthesis of arylthiopyruvic acids and some of their corresponding nitriles in order to provide easy and convenient routes for the synthesis of different types of useful products.

During studies of thiazolidones and their useful applications (Bhargava *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 49, 763, 797), it was considered worthwhile to attempt utilisation of the reactions of thiazolidones for synthesising different groups of useful chemical substances. Granacher *et al.* (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 5, 610; 1923, 6, 458) worked on the condensation reactions of aldehydes with rhodanine. Through condensation of rhodanine with homocyclic aldehydes, the corresponding homonitriles were prepared in excellent yields by Julian and Sturgis (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1126) and Cambell and McKail (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1251). By a similar condensation of 2:4-thiazolidine-dione with homocyclic aldehydes and subsequent cleavage with alkali, the corresponding thiopyruvic acids have been obtained. A similar investigation with 2-arylimino-3-aryl-4-thiazolidone and 2-arylimino-4-thiazolidone compounds, which may not exhibit the same tendency for ring fission as thiazolidine-diones, does not seem to have been undertaken. We therefore considered it of interest to examine the behaviour of thiazolidones towards these condensation reactions and to ascertain in particular the point of ring fission.

2-*o*-Tolylimino-3-*o*-tolyl-4-thiazolidone, prepared by our method (Bhargava *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) was initially condensed with benzaldehyde, *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, furfural and cinnamaldehyde, and the resulting arylidene derivatives were cleaved with alkali when aryl-substituted thiopyruvic acids were produced. Similarly 2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone, prepared by our method (*loc. cit.*), was condensed with salicylaldehyde, *m*- and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehydes, *o*- and *p*-chlorobenzaldehydes, anisaldehyde and piperonal, and the resulting arylidene derivatives were hydrolysed by alkali, when substituted thiopyruvic acids were produced. Out of these only *o*- and *p*-chlorophenylthiopyruvic acids were converted into oximino compounds with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of sodium ethoxide. The oximino compounds on treatment with acetic anhydride yield the corresponding nitriles, which provide simple and very convenient routes for the synthesis of β -substituted

ethylamine and substituted acetic acids. Preparation of nitriles has been undertaken, since these will find use in our subsequent studies on the synthesis of compounds related to natural products. The scheme of reactions is formulated as shown below :

EXPERIMENTAL

2-o-Tolylimino-3-o-tolyl-4-thiazolidone and its Arylidene Derivatives.—The preparation of 2-o-tolylimino-3-o-tolyl-4-thiazolidone, m.p. 154° (Found: N, 9.24; S, 10.79. Calc. for C₁₇H₁₆ON₂S:N, 9.46; S, 10.81%) and the condensation of the thiazolidone with various aldehydes were performed as described before (Bhargava *et. al.*, *loc. cit.*). The properties and analyses of the condensation products are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

5-Arylidene-2-o-tolylimino-3-o-tolyl-4-thiazolidones.

No.	Aldehydes.	%Yield.	Colour.	M. P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
						Found.	Calc.
1.	Benzaldehyde	89.6	Brownish yellow	95°	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ ON ₂ S	8.40	8.34
2.	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	82.7	Yellow	112°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃ S	7.39	7.46
3.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde	75.6	Orange	132°	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ ON ₃ S	7.52	7.49
4.	Furfuraldehyde	81.6	Brown	102°	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	8.60	8.55
5.	Cinnamaldehyde	88.8	Do	81°	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ ON ₂ S	7.71	7.80

2-Phenylimino-4-thiazolidone.—Phenylthiourea (6.49 g.), monochloroacetic acid (4.5 g.) and anhydrous sodium acetate (3.5 g.) in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) were refluxed for 6 hours on a water-bath. At the end of the reaction, the excess of alcohol was distilled off. The reaction mixture was poured into water, when a pale yellow precipitate was obtained. It was washed with hot water and crystallised from methyl alcohol and recrystallised from chloroform in yellow crystals, m.p. 179°, yield 80%. (Found: N, 14.63; S, 16.38. C₈H₈ON₂S requires N, 14.58; S, 16.66%).

5-Salicylidene-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone.—A mixture of salicylaldehyde (2.2 g.) and thiazolidone (3.0 g.) was dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) and to this anhydrous sodium acetate (1.2 g.) was added, and the whole was heated for 5 hours. After the reaction was over, the mixture was poured into water and the precipitate obtained was washed with sodium bisulphite and hot water and extracted with alcohol. The extract after removal of most of the alcohol was crystallised from chloroform in yellow crystals, m.p. 192°.

Similarly other aldehydes were condensed. The properties and analytical data are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

5-Arylidene-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidones.

No.	Aldehydes.	Colour.	M. P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	Salicylaldehyde	Yellow	192°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.78	10.81
2.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	Do	102°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.80	10.81
3.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	Brown	120°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.77	10.81
4.	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	Orange	184°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ON ₂ SCl	9.90	10.20
5.	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	Yellow	132°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ON ₂ SCl	9.85	10.20
6.	Anisaldehyde	Brown	94°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.28	10.40
7.	Piperonal	Yellow	147°	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ S	9.80	9.87

*Cleavage of 5-Benzylidene-2-*o*-tolylimino-3-*o*-tolyl-4-thiazolidone.*—The compound (2.0 g.) was heated with 15% NaOH (25 c.c.) under reflux over a small flame for 5 hours. A portion of the material dissolved. The undissolved material was filtered off. The alkaline filtrate was chilled in a freezing mixture and rapidly acidified with 10% HCl. The amorphous compound, phenylthiopyruvic acid, obtained was washed with water and dried, m.p. 129°.

Similarly other arylidene derivatives were cleaved with alkali. Their properties and analytical data are reported in Table III.

TABLE III

Arylthiopyruvic acids.

No.	Thiopyruvic acid.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	Phenyl-	Yellow	129°	C ₉ H ₈ O ₃ S	17.81	17.77
2.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl-	Do	134°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₃ SCl	14.37	14.68
3.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-	Brown	165°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₃ SCl	14.40	14.68
4.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl-	Yellow	116°	C ₉ H ₈ O ₃ S	16.04	16.10
5.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl-	Do	178°	C ₉ H ₈ O ₃ S	16.38	16.10
6.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl-	Do	113°	C ₉ H ₈ O ₃ S	16.43	16.10
7.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl-	Brown	158°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₄ NS	14.06	14.22
8.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-	Do	85°	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₃ S	14.98	15.23
9.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenyl-	Orange	182°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	14.47	14.35
10.	3 : 4-Methylenedioxyphenyl-	Yellow	119°	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄ S	14.07	14.27
11.	Furfuryl-	Brownish yellow	115°	C ₇ H ₆ O ₃ S	18.62	18.82
12.	Cinnamyl-	Yellow	113°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₃ S	15.62	15.53

o-Chlorophenylacetonitrile.—Sodium ethoxide (1 g. sodium in 30 c.c. of absolute alcohol) was mixed with a warm solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.0 g.) in water (5 c.c.). This was added to *o*-chlorophenylthiopyruvic acid (1.5 g.). The reaction mixture was heated for 40 minutes on a water-bath. The excess of alcohol was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in dilute NaOH and acidified with 10% HCl under cooling, when the oximino compound was precipitated. The precipitate of α -oximino-*o*-chlorophenylpyruvic acid obtained was washed and dried in a vacuum desiccator over KOH, m.p. 142°.

The oximino-acid, so prepared, was treated with acetic anhydride (20 c.c.) and heated on the water-bath till it gradually went into solution. It was refluxed for 1 hour. The acetic anhydride was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with sodium carbonate solution and water and allowed to stand over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On evaporating ether *o*-chlorophenylacetonitrile separated out, m.p. 62°.

TABLE IV

Arylacetonitriles.

No.	Acetonitrile.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		%Chlorine.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl-	62°	C ₈ H ₆ NCI	9.31	9.24	22.36	23.43
2.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-	82°	C ₈ H ₆ NCI	9.30	9.24	23.38	23.43

Similarly *p*-chlorophenylacetonitrile was prepared. The properties and analyses of *o*- and *p*-chlorophenylacetonitriles are recorded in Table IV.

ORGANIC CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY,
VARANASI.

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